

success story

ENRICHING GEOSS WITH SEMANTICS

EIFFEL ontology to tag and structure EO metadata

An **ontology** is a data model that describes a set of concepts and relationships in a particular domain, and are often used in artificial intelligence, and computer science allowing interoperability between different systems and applications.

This **interoperability**, as well as data discovery, is limited by the great heterogeneity of data sources (satellite, in-situ data, etc.), and many researchers and data scientists find it difficult to find the right datasets for their applications, since the associated metadata does not follow any specific structure. This creates a gap between producers and consumers of data, which can be solved through the use of taxonomies and ontologies. The ontology developed in EIFFEL, called **EIFF-O**, has been structured in a modular way covering three fundamental aspects:

- **General perspective:** this view covers the general need of classifying all EO datasets. This taxonomy was described by EARSC but was never implemented until now, and provides a dual vision: (i) market view, with 8 markets and 26 sectors and (ii) provider view, with 6 domains and 32 areas.
- **Specific perspective:** this view restricts the domain and scope for climate change application related to adaptation and mitigation. Primary concepts here are the Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) as specified by GCOS. This taxonomy was never implemented until now.
- **Goal-oriented perspective:** as datasets will primarily be used to develop decision-making applications, they have been linked with the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) ontology, as specified by the UN, which considers goals, targets, indicators and series.

Additionally, EIFF-O promotes the usage of **open vocabularies** (schema.org) and **formats** (JSON-LD) to allow the integration of EO datasets in the semantic web. Moreover, new ontologies and taxonomies be integrated in EIFF-O, such as the Essential Agriculture Variables (EAVs) and Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs).

The developed ontology is already available in **GitHub** to be used by the scientific community, and includes **online documentation** via readthedocs and a **video tutorial** in our YouTube channel for further information.

Useful links:

www.eiffel4climate.eu

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